

CIRCULAR PACKAGING DESIGN GUIDELINE

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Abstract: *Packaging fulfils many essential roles; from protection, storage and transport functions to aspects such as easier use and the provision of product information. These functions essentially contribute to sustainability, as packaging prevents damage to sensitive products and loss of food. In addition, the environmental impact of producing the packaged good is, in many cases, considerably greater than the impact of producing the packaging itself. In other words, both sustainable packaging design, as well as the protection of products, must be given top priority. Even though packaging can contribute to a sustainable economy, as a consumer good, its public reputation tends to be negative. Furthermore, problems such as littering, the generation of emissions and use of resources for packaging have been addressed. In recent years, a growing demand for greater sustainability in packaging design has definitely been apparent. Sustainable packaging incorporates maximum functionality and the highest possible protection of products, while keeping its ecological footprint to a minimum and enabling maximum circularity. Circular aspects of packaging have become especially important, as the European Union, in the context of the Circular Economy Package, advocates greater resource efficiency and reuse of products, considerably higher material recycling rates and the use of recycling material as a secondary raw material. The Circular Economy Package also includes the demand for a reduction of food waste, the use of non-toxic substances, as well as the increased use of bio-based raw materials. A circular approach to materials will thus protect the environment while reducing emissions. However, to achieve higher material recycling rates we need to rethink the design of packaging to improve its future recyclability while guaranteeing its functionality. In addition, we need to open up markets for the use of the secondary raw materials that are produced, which must be of a quality that enables full substitution for virgin material of the same type. The*

Circular Packaging Design Guideline aims to provide recommendations for the recyclable design of packaging systems, and addresses all actors along the entire value chain. The Guideline will be updated continuously and amended in response to changes in collection, sorting and recycling technologies, as well as future material developments. Its text should by no means be regarded as an obstacle to innovation (e.g. bio-based materials, new barrier materials etc.), on the contrary, new technologies can contribute to improving ecological performance and need to be analysed separately.

Key words: circular economy, recycling, sustainability